

APPLYING THE GRADUAL IMMERSION METHOD TO SURREALIST ART CREATION USING INTERACTIVE WHITEBOARDS

Jorge C. Sanabria, María Elena Chan, L. Rebeca Mateos, José Luis Mariscal and Jesús Arámburo-Lizárraga

Universidad de Guadalajara, Mexico

Gustavo de la Cruz

Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico

The increasing availability of information and communications technology (ICT) suggests new paradigms in informal education for educators, artists, and designers who participate in creating digital environment experiences. Creativity is perceived as a highly valued skill that contributes to greater student access to the labor market. In light of the ever-expanding usage of digital technologies and the need to develop such skills, this mixed research investigates high school students' creative process in using interactive whiteboards (IWBs), with the aim of (1) implementing a collaborative method for artistic creation and (2) enhancing the creative competencies of participants. The Gradual Immersion Method (GIM) applied here is based on intuitive familiarization with the related technology and techniques, in which groups of high school students create artistic works using a digital interface. Through a process of creative cognition in the development of digital surrealist art, based on Koestler's bisociation theory, learners are exposed to stimuli that will be intuitively recreated, shared, and evaluated by other students. The experience of learning in an open interactive environment, through the generation of surrealist artworks, enables analysis of the creative process, learning effectiveness, and the perceptual impact of learner's proposals on other viewers. The development of competencies is evaluated in terms of individual creators' profiles, the originality of the resulting digital work as perceived by fellow participants, and a creativity evaluation test.

Keywords: Gradual Immersion Method (GIM), Interactive Whiteboard (IWB), Surrealist Art, Creative Process, Bisociation Theory, High-school Students.

Introduction

The 'new industrial revolution' (Anderson, 2012) has empowered users to develop tools and methods for communication and learning supported by new technologies, e.g. portable, wearable, prototyping, and modeling devices. As a result, users have developed creative and collaborative skills more rapidly, in many cases faster than institutions can respond by tailoring their programs and curricula. Meanwhile, the importance of skills attainment is increasingly being recognized by leading organizations such as the United Nations, which has recently adopted a competency-based recruitment and benefits policy (United Nations Organization, 2015).

In response to the demand for highly skilled workers, requisite to maintain and enhance the nation's competitiveness, the Mexican Ministry of Education (SEP in Spanish) approved, in 2008, a comprehensive reform of the upper-secondary education system, which mandated that all high schools reorient their curricula toward the development of 11 competencies linked to basic education (disciplinary), labor (professional), or both (generic), which will enable students to succeed in the 21st century; among them, sensibility toward and practice of art, expression of ideas by means of graphic representations and technologies, constructive attitude for effective collaborative work, and development of innovative solutions based on established methods. However, especially given their importance, there is a notable lack of information on how to identify and develop these skills, in the context of new technologies, at the high-school level.

This leads to a critical pedagogical question as the new century unfolds: how can we sensitize teachers to explore the creative potential of students in the era of technological innovation? Given the difficulties involved in gaining access to the sophisticated equipment necessary for school-based training in the variety of competencies required by the reforms, one obvious response lies in the creation of digital environments, within existing educational institutions, for practice and rigorous study in the use of emerging technologies, to develop competencies in high schools.

As a response to the need to develop competency centered on educational technologies, Sanabria (2015) proposed the Gradual Immersion Method (GIM) as a theoretical approach to enhance creative, collaborative, and technological skills. Although capable of much broader application, in this study the GIM is specifically applied to artistic creation, promoting participants' familiarization with art and technology through intuitive practices on interactive platforms, while enhancing skills' development. In particular, the method focuses on the perceptual characteristics of art to encourage digital creation for educational purposes. For this study, a group of researchers was involved in the project's implementation in high schools, and a software program was developed to support collaborative work on IWBs within a surrealist art framework.

This is the first experience in implementing the GIM approach for educational purposes, and it is specifically aimed at (1) applying the method in the specific context of surrealist art, and (2) developing the creative skills of high-school participants, whatever their academic profile (i.e., technological, artistic, or conventional). To implement the GIM and measure creative skills, the designed software program considered three commonly studied dimensions of creativity: fluency, flexibility, and originality.

In this paper, the development of creative competencies based on the GIM is quantitatively analyzed in terms of a multifactorial creative test, for statistical accuracy in measuring creativity. Additionally, high-school students' collaborative performance in developing artworks is assessed from a qualitative perspective; and the paper concludes with the study's main findings and prospective pedagogical scenarios, to aid teachers in applying the GIM as a pedagogical method.

Literature Review

Recent Mexican high-school level policy reforms have mandated that all of the country's high schools adapt their curricula to the development of 11 competencies (SEP, 2014), which have different meanings in the different contexts of education and employment. According to SEP (2012), a competency is a "performance resulting from the mobilization of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values, as well as the skills and experiences that an individual performs in a specific context, to solve a problem or face a situation, in different stages of his/her life."

SEP has approved 11 competencies for students and 8 competencies for teachers. The 11 student skills are divided into six categories.

The student...

- A. Is self-determining and takes care of him/herself: 1. Knows and appreciates him/herself, and addresses issues and challenges, taking into account the objectives pursued. 2. Is sensitive to art

- and participates in the appreciation and interpretation of his/her expressions in different genres. 3. Selects and practices a healthy lifestyle.
- B. Expresses and communicates effectively: 4. Listens, interprets, and delivers relevant messages in different contexts using media tools and appropriate codes.
- C. Thinks critically and reflectively: 5. Develops innovations and proposes solutions to problems based on established methods. 6. Holds a personal position on issues of global concern and relevance, and considers other points of view critically and reflectively.
- D. Learns autonomously: 7. Learns through his/her own initiative, and based on his/her own interests, throughout life.
- E. Works collaboratively: 8. Participates and collaborates effectively in diversified teams.
- F. Participates responsibly in society: 9. Participates in the life of his/her community, region, country, and the world, with civic and ethical awareness. 10. Maintains a respectful attitude toward multiculturalism and diversity of beliefs, values, ideas, and social practices. 11. Contributes critically and with responsible actions toward sustainable development.

According to SEP, the competencies are founded on the following criteria: they have a holistic and integrated character; they are in constant development; they are conceived in different contexts of both intervention and evaluation; they are integrated through a permanent process of critical reflection; they vary in their development and level of achievement according to the degrees of complexity and control; and they spur a change in the logic of didactic transposition. From Cobo and Moravec's perspective (2011), learning models should be continuous, concentrated, and flexible, so that they will not only be a source of information (reiteration of contents) but foster the development of skills that address the needs of the current context. They agree with Blikstein's view (2013) that neither the use of technological devices, nor the incorporation of academic certificates and international quality standards, are sufficient to guarantee effective learning; and add that education demands ecological and systemic improvement, and sustained, culturally inclusive results, supported by a "broad framework of competencies, knowledge, and skills that may be adopted, according to the context, to increase the level of employability, promote the formation of 'knowledge brokers,' or expand the dimensions of traditional learning."

However, how to evaluate such competency-based performance remains a challenge. Moreover, in addition to the traditional (i.e., conventional) school curriculum, high schools typically focus on disciplines such as arts, technologies, medicine, or gastronomy; structural diversity which may explain why institutions rarely identify or exploit the manifold opportunities provided by digital technologies increasingly used by students both inside and outside of school, leaving students to develop skills that go unnoticed and unsupported by their teachers—what Cobo and Moravec refer to as "invisible learning" (2011).

Identifying and developing creative competencies is especially important for future engineers and technologists. According to the National Institute of Statistics and Geography (INEGI in Spanish) and the National Association of Universities and Institutions of Higher Education (ANUIES in Spanish), Mexico graduates more engineers than any other nation on the continent—roughly 115,000 annually. This vigorous engineering base, combined with its geo-strategic position, enables Mexico to maintain a high level of competitiveness in the manufacture of products and technologies. For instance, the aviation industry in Mexico has witnessed annual growth of nearly 20% over the past ten years, with aerospace exports valued at US\$4.33 billion in 2011, and expected to grow to US\$12.27 trillion by 2021. Currently in Mexico there are 249 aerospace-related companies employing some 31,000 highly qualified professionals (ProMéxico, 2012). Given the importance of maintaining and improving the level of innovation throughout the country, it is imperative to continually research current creativity-development methods involving technological advances, to enable students to develop their skills, and teachers to identify and enhance those skills.

Creativity, often defined in terms of the capacity to produce new or original ideas (Goldschmidt, 2005), is considered to be relevant when framed by an application context; for instance, when applied to artistic expression or the engineering of a device. According to Smith et al. (2010), it is generally

represented by educational researchers as involving three aspects that overlap with both areas (creativity and education):

- The use of creativity (or insight) to solve problems in other subject areas
- Creative ideas for teaching
- Teaching for, or attempting to enhance, the creativity of children.

Methods to enhance creativity vary in their application. Kowaltowski et al. (2009) conducted research on 250 methods for stimulating creativity, including AIDA, brainstorming, and focus groups. Their study showed that a significant number of methods relate to areas such as psychology, pedagogy, marketing, fine arts, or engineering design, but for certain contexts (e.g., architecture), even though teachers are concerned about enhancing students' creativity, the tools that could increase creativity are mainly applied informally, and are not clearly identified as methods, techniques, or tools.

Koestler's (1964) concept of the creative process, known as bisociation, is fundamental to the context of this study, in which powerful stimuli have been used as both the primary source of inspiration and the primary object of creation. His theory illustrates the natural combination of creative thinking supported by the cognitive process involved in recognizing patterns, synthesizing, and the association of ideas. For Koestler, creative acts originate in the connection of previously unrelated dimensions of experience. He represents this notion by means of a diagram in which two frames of reference¹, differing in nature and with apparently no relationship, may yet intersect and simultaneously "vibrate", thereby generating a new association not contained in the original frames. From the cognitive psychology point of view, such 'bisociation' belongs to the realm of conceptual synthesis. Following Koestler, Finke et al. (1992) examined major cognitive theories that seek to understand the creative process regarding preinventive structures such as mental blends, schemas, and mental models. They characterize bisociation as the sudden collision of contrary patterns of thought that may result in humor, new discoveries, and/or aesthetic experiences. Examples of visual stimuli conveying bisociated characteristics are often found in the fine arts, particularly in Surrealist artworks portraying illogical, dreamlike scenes. Due to its powerful impact, and the ubiquitous presence of bisociation in its artworks, the Surrealist art movement was chosen for this study. In the present context of research on creativity, bisociation acts as a stimulus, originating in Surrealist artworks, which enables the method not only to enhance creativity but to work as an instrument for measuring it as well.

There is consensus about the common dimensions that a creativity test may include: fluency (quantity of ideas), flexibility (variety of ideas), originality (novelty of ideas) and elaboration (details of opinions) (Guilford, 1950, 1967; Torrance 1966; Amabile, 1983; Paulus, 2000; Cohen & Swerdluk, 2009). In consideration of the Mexican context, among the different instruments used to measure creativity in educational contexts, the Multifactorial Evaluation of Creativity (MUEC) test (Sánchez et al., 2009) was selected for this study. Specifically designed for adolescents, the MUEC focuses on three main indicators of creativity: fluency, flexibility, and originality. It is often used in creativity tests, and has been validated in a variety of scenarios (Sánchez et al., 2009; Sánchez, 2009; García, 2009). Thus, the same three indicators have been integrated into the GIM, in order to allow for comparison of the GIM and MUEC results.

In light of the foregoing, a GIM-based application for collaborative creative work was developed, and tested with high-school students, using IWBs.

Method

Participants and Setting

A total of 42 participants, from three Mexican high schools, voluntarily participated in the experiment, which was conducted in a laboratory-like space at the MIND building in the city of Guadalajara, Mexico.

¹ Koestler coined the term 'matrices of thought', as a unifying formula of the terms 'frames of reference', 'associative contexts', 'universes of discourse', 'types of logic', 'codes of behavior', etc.

Three workshop-style studies were conducted with students ranging from 16 to 18 years old, coming from two of three different curricular profiles each time: art-centered (the CEDART school), technology-centered (CETI-Colomos) and conventional (High School No. 7, UDG). Each study was approximately three hours in duration, with 10-minute hourly breaks; and involved 12 to 16 different students divided into four teams. The teams were named Alpha, Beta, Gamma and Delta, and members were given ID cards with a personal code (A1, A2...; B1, B2...; etc.), to be input whenever they performed an individual task among the GIM tasks, and to identify themselves in the MUEC test.

The generic set-up consisted of four IWBs in a square in the center of the room, with four chairs in front of each, on which the three- or four-student teams sat and interacted with the application. The experiment was coordinated by the main researcher, who guided the students, and supported by facilitators who were familiar with the application tools. One facilitator was assigned to each team, to keep time, help with application issues, and address student requests.

Transportation to and from the students' schools was provided. At the end of the experiment, students were offered a meal and a tour of the MIND building.

Apparatus and Materials

Two instruments were used in the experiment: a software application run as an interface on interactive white boards (IWBs), and a paper-and-pencil test to measure creativity.

Four 87-inch multi-touch IWBs were used for running the GIM tasks. These are vertically standing systems that use an ultra-short-throw high-offset projector which allows high-performance interactivity while reducing shadows and glare. Each IWB was connected to a personal computer on which the software was run.

The Art Movement Learning Application (AMLA) is software, based on the GIM, specially designed for students to conduct the activities, in order to develop their creative skills by means of surrealist artwork creation. It was designed with an eye to the collaborative possibilities offered by IWBs, and further capabilities for mixed reality environments. Although the AMLA's architecture was developed to support broader activities regarding art movements, for the purpose of this study it was aimed at familiarizing users with certain characteristics of Surrealism, while immersing them in digital creation.

The interface was set to work with a multi-touch IWB, in order to allow intuitive interaction by the participants. It consisted of six tasks, based on the GIM: observation, combination, association, grouping, discernment, and evaluation; and was designed both for tactile performance and for receiving written input from a digital keyboard.

The materials shown in the interface consisted of pictures of humans, animals, and/or objects; bisociated images (a combination of humans, animals, and/or objects); as well as surrealist and other artworks (traditional or digital) containing bisociated features. The bisociated materials were selected from the Web by researchers and design or art specialists, according to the following criteria: images combined two elements in an incongruent relationship, but evoked an emergent third image—in the viewer's mind.

The Multifactorial Evaluation of Creativity (MUEC) test is a paper-and-pencil instrument that assesses creative competencies based on three dimensions (also incorporated into the evaluative design of the GIM): fluency, flexibility, and originality. It consists of three sections, involving a total of five tasks, focusing respectively on visuomotor creativity, applied creativity, and verbal creativity, each in terms of the three dimensions above.

Conditions and Design

The experiment consisted of two stages: GIM tasks on the IWBs, followed by the MUEC test. Each of the GIM tasks was initiated with a screen showing the instructions, and ended with a screen announcing the end of the respective stage. Students were requested to follow the instructions, conduct the respective activities accordingly, and only continue to the next stage when all the teams had finished a given

activity. Interaction with the screen was solely tactile, including typing on a digital keyboard. The sequence of tasks was as follows.

Task I: Observation. Approximate duration: 30 min. On-screen instructions: “Observe the following images. Then individually type in the common characteristics shared by these images.” (These images are bisociated.)

Task II: Combination. Approximate duration: 50 min. On-screen instructions: “Based on the characteristics input in the previous task, create a collaborative artwork using two images from the folders (humans, animals, objects) provided, and then an individual artwork in the same manner.” (These images are not bisociated, but are to be combined by the students themselves.)

Task III: Association. Approximate duration: 15 min. On-screen instructions: “Drag the following floating images to their appropriate location in the main artwork.”

Task IV: Grouping. Approximate duration: 40 min. On-screen instructions: “Observe the following images, then drag them to make groups according to your team’s perception of their characteristics. Use the keyboard to put a name on each group.”

Task V: Discernment. Approximate duration: 10 min. On-screen instructions: “From the following pair of artworks, choose the one that best corresponds to the characteristics of the images you have seen over the entire sequence of activities.”

Task VI: Evaluation. Approximate duration: 30 min. On-screen instructions: “Read the definitions of ‘flexibility’ and ‘originality’ on the screen, and then individually evaluate the artworks made by other team members, using the Flexibility and Originality scales provided, where ‘0’ is none, and ‘12’ is the maximum value.”

Following the GIM tasks, students were guided to a room with desks and chairs, in order to answer the MUEC test.

As aforementioned, the MUEC test consists of five tasks to be completed in paper-and-pencil format. Students were directed by the main researcher, who read the instructions for each section and kept the time. The following were the instructions for the MUEC test activities.

- Section 1: Visuomotor Creativity (I). “Create a drawing in the left square provided, using the strokes provided to the right; you may add more shapes. You have three minutes to make the drawing.”
- Section 2: Visuomotor Creativity (II). Same instructions as above.
- Section 3: Applied Creativity (I). “You will be shown an image. Consider, and then write down all the possible uses you can imagine for the object presented. You have two minutes to complete this task.”
- Section 4: Applied Creativity (II). Same instructions as above.
- Section 5: Verbal Creativity. “You are presented with six words. Create a story that includes all the words. You should write a beginning, a development of the story, and an end. You have five minutes to finish the task.”

Procedure

Two types of assessment were applied with respect to student creative capability. Students worked (sometimes individually) in groups of three to four members in performing the GIM tasks in the AMLA interface, and subsequently answered the MUEC test individually. Both the MUEC and GIM evaluations focused on the three aforementioned dimensions, often used to measure creativity: fluency, flexibility, and originality. The scales ranged from 0 to 12, with 0 indicating the complete absence of a given quality,

and 12 its dominant presence. The students’ MUEC results were evaluated by the researchers; the GIM’s flexibility and originality results were evaluated by peer students using the scales in Task VI; and the GIM’s fluency results were evaluated by the researchers, in terms of the number of ideas input in Task I. To assess the similarity in measurement accuracy between the respective dimensional scales in the GIM and the MUEC, Student’s t-test was used with a 95 percent confidence level. To compare the results for the three curricular-profile groups, a one-way ANOVA was applied, with the same confidence level.

Data Analysis – Comparison of the MUEC and GIM scales

Student’s t-test was used to compare the results of both instruments (MUEC and GIM) in measuring the level of creativity, with the hypothesis that there would be no significant difference in the respective measurement results; that is, that the evaluation scales of both instruments are equally reliable for measuring the three dimensions of creativity: fluency, flexibility, and originality. The results in Table 1 confirmed this hypothesis.

Table 1. T-test: Paired two sample for means for the MUEC and GIM.

<i>Methods</i>	MUEC	GIM
Mean	5.92	5.52
Variance	1.96	3.24
Observations	42	42
Pearson Correlation	0.29	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
dt	41	
t Stat	1.32	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.09	
t Critical one-tail	1.68	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.19	
t Critical two-tail	2.01	

N = 42

A confidence level of 95% is observed, thus the hypothesis of equality between the two method scales is confirmed. Specifically, the difference between the means is 0.40; therefore, the hypothesized means equals zero. Thus, there is sufficient evidence to suggest that both approaches, the GIM and the MUEC, measure the same dimensions (fluency, flexibility, and originality) with equal reliability.

Data Analysis – MUEC

The research group analyzed the results of the MUEC test using the specifications table provided with the test. The various sections of the test required students to draw or write imaginative solutions or scenarios in order to complete the five tasks established for the visuomotor, applied, and verbal creativity sections.

Overall, the art-centered students’ performance was outstanding compared to the other two groups (viz. number of shapes, ideas, and words). The participants’ familiarity with expressing their ideas through drawings and writing may have positively influenced both their MUEC and GIM scores.

Descriptive Statistics – ANOVA of MUEC

We observed significant differences, at a 95 percent confidence level, between the respective means of the evaluation scores of the three groups (art, technology, conventional). Participants with an artistic profile showed greater creative talent in comparison to those with conventional or technological profiles, which latter presented similar results. Additionally, the evaluation scores' variability was greater in the case of the art-centered students, given the variance value.

Table 2. One-way ANOVA analysis of the MUEC test

Summary						
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	
Art	11	80.5	7.31	1.88	1.37	
Conventional	15	80.66	5.37	1.37	1.17	
Technology	16	87.5	5.46	0.90	0.94	
ANOVA						
<i>Source of variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Among groups	29.17	2	14.58	11.04	0	3.23
Within groups	51.50	39	1.32			
Total	80.67	41				

N = 42

Data Analysis – GIM

The GIM results showed that participants were able to abstract the characteristics of the bisociated images shown in the project. Some of the answers provided by students when asked to input the characteristics of the observed images in the first stage of the GIM were:

- *Our brain tends to relate the images even though they have no apparent relation to each other, not even the whole image itself has an association to our schemas but its composition and juxtaposition makes us think it does—it's all about perspective.*
- *From a set of various objects you may create a completely different image (...) one of the objects may be the complement of another object (...).*
- *The elements that constitute the images have no relation to the final image.*
- *Some cases combined two completely opposite elements, but when conjoined they could illustrate different concepts.*
- *Images showed real objects combined in a different way, which creates the illusion of something totally different from what they were before combining them, with different functions and characteristics.*
- *The techniques to combine objects are not the same in all images.*
- *Some images comprise objects from the past deployed in a present-day context, or use objects to form animals, or to combine parts of animals with others.*
- *Images were more than what they seemed to be, hybrids between humans, machines or animals.*
- *Images are formed by different objects, animated or lifeless, to encompass a single idea.*
- *Images are transformations of their original state. Beyond their mere functionality, the objects show aesthetic features.*

- *Images use daily objects to create an atmosphere from an association.*
- *Objects are positioned in a way that generates an optical illusion that makes you think of other objects.*
- *[Images are] combinations intimating evolution.*

The answers reveal a high level of student assimilation of the key characteristics of the stimuli provided, even though these were only Task 1 (Observation) answers, and the students had not yet even begun to create artistic expressions based on the characteristics of the images observed.

In the collaborative work, students gradually developed confidence in sharing their ideas with other members of their team. They also demonstrated rapid familiarization with the software (i.e., rapidly required less direction from their facilitators as the successive stages of the project evolved). Illustrating the notion of collaboration described by Dillenbourg (1999), students’ task negotiations were highly and consistently collaborative, rather than hierarchical with one member issuing instructions.

Descriptive Statistics – ANOVA of the GIM

Variance analysis of the GIM suggested that the study groups (art-centered, technology-centered, and conventional curricula) showed no significant differences in their evaluation scores from a statistical perspective, from which we may infer that the GIM allows students to develop their creative skills independently of their school curricular profile. In particular, we observed that, on average, the art-centered and conventional profile groups received similar scores in the evaluations (6.06 and 5.93, respectively); and that the technology-centered group, despite their familiarity with the use of such technologies, had a significantly lower overall average (4.77). The scores of conventional profile participants showed considerable data variability, likely due to the lack of specialization, and therefore greater heterogeneity, among these students.

Table 3. One-way ANOVA analysis of the GIM

Summary						
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	
Art	11	66.69	6.06	1.34	1.15	
Conventional	15	88.97	5.93	5.03	2.24	
Technology	16	76.34	4.77	2.29	1.51	
ANOVA						
<i>Source of variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Among groups	14.74	2	7.37	2.42	0.10	3.23
Within groups	118.37	39	3.03			
Total	133.12	41				

N = 42

Overall, our analysis suggested that the GIM has significant potential for stimulating and enhancing the creative skills of students characterized by any of the three broad curricular profiles sampled here.

A possible explanation for why art education has a favorable impact on school and corporate performance is that it allows individuals to flexibilize their behavior. Behavioral flexibility refers to the human ability to select and utilize ambient information, a key factor in people’s adaptation to society;

therefore, it is understood that in the process of perception there are sensorial as well as social aspects involved (Vargas, 1994). Collaborating with others in the creation of artworks, employing different perceptual means of sharing and understanding what others observe, contributes, in the broader social context, to the amplification of conceptual references, and the formation of new ones (as in Koestler's approach); and to alternative means of establishing associations between elements in the environment. Based on the results of our study, it may be inferred that an amplification of conceptual references was identified, since negotiation was observed among participants in order to establish common criteria regarding the bisociated images in the GIM tasks (Dillenbourg, 1999).

Conclusions

The GIM and MUEC scales measured the same factors: fluency, flexibility, and originality. However, the GIM evaluation showed less difference between the means of the three groups (art, conventional, technology), which suggests that the GIM facilitates students' expression and development of their creative skills; suggesting that the method has significant viability as a means of both evaluating and stimulating the creative skills of high school students.

Experimentation demonstrated the importance of technology-supported collaborative work, as well as the effectiveness of the GIM method in enhancing creativity and learning. The interactive method fosters the development of collaborative skills central to the competency framework mandated for the Mexican educational system at the high school level; however, the listening, interpreting and consensus-forming skills fostered by the GIM are equally important in the corporate environment.

As discussed earlier, Koestler's theory suggests a creative process characterized by two different frames of reference, with combinations of contrastive elements (e.g., abilities, habits, rules, etc.) (Dubitzky et al., 2012). Based on this theory, it may be thought that the greater MUEC and GIM scores of the art-centered students reflected a learning-history foundation that enabled them to relate to foreign reference frames, typically composed of elements associated with the arts, more effectively than the members of the other groups (conventional and technical). This provides enhanced conditions for convergence to occur; that is, for an increased number of possible relations and associations among reference-frame elements, beyond those already possessed by the art-centered students. And this argues for the importance of strengthening the role and presence of the arts within general education, and of fostering creativity through methods such as the GIM.

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